

Revision and LLM tools

This survey aims at understanding the use and potential of LLM tools (generative AI) for revising translations. It targets revisers with or without experience with LLM tools.

People responsible for the study are:

Filling out this questionnaire may require between 5 and 20 minutes.

The survey will be available until April 15.

For questions or queries, you can email us at:

There are 23 questions in this survey.

Data management and consent

Before we can start, we need to be sure you consent to participate in this study.

Here are some information about data management:

Your answers to the survey will be collected completely anonymously. We have no way of linking your answers to your identity. In fact, we will not record any personal data that could identify you. Since the survey is completely anonymous, we will not be able to follow up on your participation or destroy your answers once they have been submitted. If you want to withdraw while taking part in the survey, simply type "I withdraw" in any free text field.

The data will be safely stored and archived under the responsibility of [REDACTED] for an unlimited period of time.

Consent question 1 *

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

I have read and understood the information about the study

Consent question 2 *

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

I am participating in this study voluntarily

Consent question 3 *

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

I agree that the data from this survey may be used for scientific purposes (e.g., conferences or publications)

Introduction (1/2)

Do you revise translations?

Here is how we define "revision" or "revising": checking and, if necessary, amending a translation prepared by someone else, or recommending such amendments

*

Please choose **only one** of the following:

Yes

No

Introduction (2/2)

Have you ever used an LLM (generative AI) tool for revision (ChatGPT, Copilot, Gemini...)? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

Yes

No

Could you tell us why you have never used an LLM tool for revision? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

[G04Q07.NAOK](#) == "N")

Please write your answer here:

Uses of LLMs

Have you used an LLM for real revision jobs or were you just experimenting?

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

Real jobs

Experimenting

Both

Have you used the following LLM tools for revision?

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

ChatGPT

Copilot

Gemini

Other:

Altogether, how many times have you used an LLM tools **to revise real revision jobs**?

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

Never

Once

2–3 times

4–9 times

10 times or more

Altogether, how many times have you used an LLM tool **to experiment with revision**?

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

Never

Once

2–3 times

4–9 times

10 times or more

In which language combination(s) did you use the tool(s)? Please indicate the direction of translation along with the two languages (e.g. German-to-French).

Please write your answer here:

Was the target language of the translations you revised your first language?

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Always
- Often
- Sometimes
- Never

Would you like to share your impressions of the tool(s) you have used?

Please write your answer here:

Profile

You are almost done! This is the last section.

We just need some information about you:

In which country do you live?

Please write your answer here:

How would you define yourself? (more than one option possible)

Select all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- in-house translator
- freelance translator
- researcher
- teacher in languages/translation
- translation student

Other:

Please enter your age:

Please write your answer here:

What are your languages?

Comment only when you choose an answer.

Please choose all that apply and provide a comment:

L1

L2

L3

L4

L5

For how many years have you been **translating**?

Please write your answer here:

For how many years have you been **revising**?

Please write your answer here:

Thank you very much for taking part in this survey!

05-05-2025 – 11:02

Submit your survey.

Thank you for completing this survey.